

MIRZA MEHDI KHAN'S WORK "MABANI'L-LUGHAT": GRAMMAR OF THE OLD UZBEK LANGUAGE IN PERSIAN

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Abstract. *Among the philological works devoted to the study of Mir Alishir Navoi's language, Mirza Mehdi Khan's dictionary "Sanglakh" with a grammatical essay "Mabani'l-Lughat" ("Basics of the Language") (18th century) is particularly noteworthy. Compared to others, it is the first valuable and more reliable work on the grammar of the old Uzbek language.*

In 1172-1173 of the Islamic calendars, Mirza Mehdi Khan concluded his philological work, entitled "Sanglakh". Four folios of this work by Mirza Mehdi Khan are known to exist. The Gibb Foundation holds the first of these, the second is located in the British Museum, the third is in the Bodleian Library at the University of Oxford, and the fourth is in the Sulaymaniye Library in Turkey. An abridged version of the "Sanglakh" held at the Bibliothèque Nationale in Paris. The text was transcribed by Muhamed Huwayi for the ruler Abbas Mirza and is known as the "Hulasa-yi Abbasi".

"Mabani'l-Lughat" is divided into three sections: a preface, a grammar section, and six sections, or bases, which describe various grammatical forms and phenomena.

This article presents an analysis of the grammatical system of "Mabani'l-Lughat". The grammatical material of "Maboniu-l-lughat" introduces Mirza Mehdi Khan as a Persian Turkologist and the author of the first scientific grammar of Uzbek language.

The study of the grammatical material of "Mabani'l-Lughat" is of great importance in solving a number of problematic issues related to the history of Uzbek language and for compiling a historical grammar of Uzbek language.

Keywords: *Mirza Mehdi Khan, Sanglakh, Mabani'l-Lughat, Navayi, Old Uzbek language, Chaghatay language, Tarsif, Mabna.*

It is notable that a number of significant sources for the study of the Old Uzbek language [14:83-89; 16:1-13; 3:176-177; 18] can be found in philological works written in the Persian language during the 16th and 17th centuries. These include dictionaries such as: 1) "Bada'i al-lughat" [6] by Tali' Kherevi; 2) Abushqa [12:264; 7:532-533]; 3) "Lughat-i Turki" [12:264] by Fazlullahan; 4) "Kelurnama" dictionary-guide by Muhammad Chingi [12:264]; 5) "Sanglakh" by Mehdi Khan with a grammatical essay "Mabani'l-Lughat"; 6) Fath Alikhan [16:83-99].

Notably, some significant sources for the study of the Old Uzbek language can be found in philological works written in the Persian language during the 16th and 17th centuries. Among such philological works, Mirza Mehdi Khan's dictionary "Sanglakh" with a grammatical essay "Mabani'l-Lughat" ("Basics of the Language") [15:3-12; 18:58-59; 13:65-71; 9:156-220; 4; 10], which has long attracted the attention of domestic and foreign linguists, is particularly noteworthy. The study of Mehdi Khan's "Mabani'l-Lughat" is of great importance for resolving several problematic issues related to the history of Uzbek language, in particular, the grammar of the Old Uzbek language.

While numerous phenomena of the Old Uzbek language were discussed in the scientific works of P.M.Melioransky, A.K.Borovkov, N.A.Baskakov, A.N.Kononov, V.V.Reshetov,

A.G.Gulyamov, V.V.Radlov, K.K.Yudakhin, A.M.Shcherbak, G.F.Blagov, S.E.Malov, K.Brockelman, V.D.Artamoshin, V.M.Nasilov, G.A.Abdurakhmanov, S.Mutallibov, K.Karimov, E.I.Fazilov, Sh.Shukurov, K.Makhmudov, and others [19:4], there are still some fundamental issues that require further investigation. A comprehensive analysis of Mirza Mehdi Khan's "Mabani'l-Lughat" could potentially shed light on these matters and facilitate the resolution of these issues. Additionally, this work by Mehdi Khan offers valuable insights into the historical development of grammatical studies [1].

The objective of this paper is to elucidate Mehdi Khan's grammatical system and the study of the grammatical material of "Mabani'l-Lughat".

Mirza Mehdi Khan was born in Astrabad. His full name was Nizam al-Din Muhammad Hadi al-Husayni al-Safavi, and his father's name was Mirza Muhammad Nasiri. Mehdi Khan served as a scribe and historiographer for the Iranian ruler Nadir Shah, who lived in the 19th century. He participated in military campaigns and fulfilled political assignments for the Shah.

In the year 1172-1173 of the Islamic calendar, Mirza Mehdi Khan concluded his philological work, entitled "Sanglakh". Four folios of this work by Mirza Mehdi Khan are currently known to exist. The Gibb Foundation holds the first of these, the second is located in the British Museum, the third is in the Bodleian Library at the University of Oxford, and the fourth is in the Sulaymaniye Library in Turkey. An abridged version of the "Sanglakh" held at the Bibliothèque Nationale in Paris. The text transcribed by Muhamed Huwayi for the ruler Abbas Mirza and known as the "Hulasa-yi Abbasi" [12: 264-266].

"Mabani'l-Lughat" [8] – the grammatical section of the "Sanglakh" was published in lithographic format by English orientalist E. Denison Ross in 1910 in Calcutta, derived from a manuscript from the Gibb collection. In 1950, B. Atalay published the same section in Istanbul. This was done using the same method from a manuscript belonging to the Sulaymaniye Library in Turkey. Subsequently, in 1967, it was the subject of an investigation in Uzbekistan by the orientalist Z. Umarov [19]. In 1960, J. Clawson produced a facsimile edition of the "Sanglakh" [17] manuscript from the Gibb collection. In the following years it was researched by Q. Muhitdinov [11].

The initial chapter of the thesis is dedicated to an exposition of Mehdi Khan's grammatical system.

The work, entitled "Mabani'l-Lughat", comprises a preface, a grammar section, and six sections or bases, considered as subsections.

The preface to the "Mabani'l-Lughat" sets forth the rationale for composing the grammatical essay and enumerates twelve poetic and nine prose works by Navoi that he drew upon in his writing. In addition to five poems of "Khamasa" and four divans, the following works by Alisher Navoi are included in the list: "Lisanu-t-Tayr" ("The Language of Birds"), "Arba'ini Manzum" ("The Four poems"), "Nazmu-l-Jawahir" ("The threading of the pearls"), "Mahbubu-l-Qulub" ("A Loved Heart"), "Mezanu-l-Awzan" ("The Scales of the sizes"), "Khamsatu-l-Mutahayyirin" ("Five Fanciers"), "Nasaimu-l-Muhabbat" ("Zephyrs of Love"), "Tarikhu-l-Anbiye" ("History of the Prophets"), and "Tarikhi muluki Ajam" ("The history about Persian kings"). Additionally, the following works by Alisher Navoi are included in the list: "Majalisu-n-Nafayis" ("The set of fanciers"), "Munshaat" ("The Letters"), and "Waqfnama-i Madrasa-i Ikhlasiya" (A record of Ikhlasiyya Madrasa, as documented in the Vakuf archives).

Furthermore, the author in the preface highlights the distinctive grammatical characteristics of Turki languages, which are not reflected in either Persian or Arabic (“Mabani’l-Lughat”, p. 5).

Tarsif notes that in Arabic, the basis of the verb is the masdar-infinitive, whereas, in Uzbek, the imperative mood of the second-person singular is used. The remaining verb forms derived through the addition of specific affixes to the imperative mood.

The initial section, designated as the “first mabna”, is comprised of ten chapters. The initial chapter is dedicated to the masdar – infinitive (مصادر *masādir*), encompassing illustrative examples of assorted verb nouns and participles, and encompassing an examination of the category of voice (passive-reflexive voice, reciprocal voice, causative verb).

The second chapter sets forth a description of the past tense forms, which he refers by the term “فعل ماضی” (*fe’l-i māzi*). Mehdi Khan refers to the past tense forms as the past categorical past tense forms of *-di, -di / -ti, -ti*, past participles of *-p, -ban, -bān* past participles of *-mish, mish, ghan / -gān, -kan* and the form *-maidur, -mäidür*.

The third chapter addresses the present-future forms (فعل مضارع *fe’l-i mozāre*). In addition to the aforementioned forms, the author includes the present participle form of *-r*, as well as the forms of *-ghai / -gāi, -kāi, -sun, -sün, -dik, -a*.

The fourth chapter is dedicated to the description of the Arabic اسم فاعل *ism-i fa’el* (Present tense), which used to denote the agent or subject of a verb. In this section, Mehdi Khan includes the active participle in *-ghuchi / -güchi, -küchi, -a+ghan / -a+gān, -r* as well as the names of professions formed by affixes *-chi, -chi, -vul, -ghun, -qun / -gün, -kün, -chaq*. The forms of the desirable inclination in *-ghur, -qur / -gür, -kür*, based on illustrative examples, are also attributed to the names of the active person, with the aforementioned forms being translated into Persian using participial forms.

The fifth chapter is dedicated to the forms of the past tenses, which in the author’s terminology designated as (اسم مفعول *ism-i maf’ul*). This encompasses the aforementioned forms. The suffixes *-mish, -mish, -ghan / -gān, -kän, -ligh, -lik, -lugh, -lük, -ghun / -gün, -kün* are also included.

The sixth chapter provides an analysis of the imperative mood (فعل امر *fe’l-i amr*). The text provides a list of affixes that are used to form the imperative mood.

It is of considerable interest to note the form of the imperative mood of the third person singular with *-dik*, which is preserved in some colloquialisms of southern Tajikistan.

Chapter seven presents an analysis of the negative imperative mood.

The eighth chapter addresses the formation of negative verb forms (فعل نفي *fe’l-i nafi*). It provides an overview of the various methods employed in the creation of these forms.

The ninth chapter is dedicated to the adverbial participle, which Mehdi Khan refers to as حال *hāl*. The following chapter addresses the de-particles *-a, -ä, -y, -yu, -yü*.

The tenth chapter sets forth the methods for attaching affixes and root bases, that is, affixing affixes to root bases with and without modification.

In the second mabna, the author provides an account of the phonetic variants of verbal affixes and an analysis of their usage.

The third mabna is devoted to the study of pronouns. Mehdi Khan refers to demonstrative pronouns as “demonstrative nouns” (اسماء اشاره *asmā-i ishāra*). The pronouns are divided into two categories: independent pronouns (ضمایر منفصله *zamāyir-i munfasila*), which include personal

pronouns and copula (مين -*men*, سين -*sen*, بيز -*biz*, سيز -*siz*); and fused pronouns (ضمائر متصله *zamāir-i muttasila*), to which he attributes the affixes of belonging.

The following diagram illustrates the “Mabani’l-Lughat” grammatical system

The fourth mabna provides a comprehensive list and detailed characterization of the affixes, which are referred to in the above work by the term حرف *harf*.

The fifth mabna is dedicated to the examination of words that possess grammatical meanings in addition to their lexical meanings. This mabna also delineates the auxiliary and modal meanings of the verbs الماق *almaq*, توشماک *tüşhmäk*, بیلماک *bilmäk*, کیریشماک *kirishmäk*, یازماق *yazmaq*, کورماک *körmäk*.

The sixth mabna provides an overview of the principles of Old Uzbek orthography and highlights some distinctive features of the spelling of native and loanwords employed in Alisher Navoi’s works. The following diagram can express the grammatical system that is evident in Mehdi Khan’s work.

In light of the aforementioned evidence, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Mehdi Khan’s “Mabani’l-Lughat” represents a significant and comprehensive contribution to the field of Old Uzbek grammar.
2. The study of the grammatical material of “Mabani’l-Lughat” is of significant value in addressing a number of questions pertaining to the history of Uzbek language and in the compilation of a historical grammar of Uzbek language.
3. The distinction made by Mehdi Khan between ‘qāf’ and ‘kāf’ bases, as well as the phonetic variants of affixes, provides a rationale for considering the Old Uzbek language to be singarmonic.
4. The “Mabani’l-Lughat” provides insight into the Old Uzbek language, reflecting forms that have not survived in modern Turkic languages. This is of significant cognitive value.

REFERENCES

1. Alimova, K. Z. (2024). MIRZO MEHDIKHAN'S WORK "MABONIUI-L-LUG'AT" AND ITS PLACE IN TURKOLOGY. *Oriental Journal of Philology*, 4(03), 425-434.

2. Alimova, K. Z. (2024). IN THE WORKS OF IRANIAN AND AFGHAN LINGUISTS INTERPRETATION OF PRIMARY CATEGORY OF THE VERB. *Oriental Journal of Philology*, 4(03), 21-28.
3. Baskakov N.A. Tyurkskiye yazyki (Turkic languages). Moscow, 1960, pp.176-177.
4. Besim Atalay. Mirza Mehdi Mehmet Han. Senglah. Lugat-i Nevai. Istanbul, 1950.
5. Borovkov A.K. Leksikograficheskaya traditsiya v slovaryakh chagatayskogo yazyka (Lexicographical tradition in dictionaries of the Chagatai language). Lexicographical collection, issue IV. Moscow, 1960, pp.151-162.
6. Borovkov A.K. Bada'i al-lugat slovar' Tali' Imani Geratskogo k sochineniyam Alishera Navoi (Bada'i al-lughat dictionary of Tali' Imani of Herat to the works of Alisher Navoi). Moscow, 1961.
7. Catalogue des manuscrits et xylographes orientaux de la Bibliothèque Impériale Publique de St. Pétersbourg. SPb., 1852, pp.532-533.
8. Denison Ross. The Mabâni'l-lughat being a grammar of the turki language in Persian by Mirzâ Mehdi Khân, Bibl. Indica, New Series № 1225. – Calcutta, 1910.
9. Eckmann J. Mirza Mehdis Darstellung der tschagataischen Sprache. – Analecta Orientalia memorial Al. Csoma de Kőrös dicata. Budapest, 1942-1947, pp.156-220.
10. Menges K.N. Das Cagatajische in der persischen Darstellung von Mirza Mahdi Han. Mainz, 1956.
11. Mukhitdinov K. “Sanglakh” Mirzy Mukhameda Mekhdikhana (Issledovaniye, kommentarii, perevod i transkriptsiya) (“Sanglakh” by Mirza Muhammad Mehdikhan (Research, comments, translation and transcription)): Abstract of the thesis. Tashkent, 1971, 27 p.
12. Rieu Charles. Catalogue of the Turkish manuscripts in the British Museum. London, 1887, pp.263-266.
13. Rasulov R. O'zbek tilini o'rganish tarixidan (From the history of learning the Uzbek language). Scientific notes of the Andijan State Pedagogical Institute. № 2. Andijan, 1955, pp.65-71.
14. Romaskevich A.A. Novyj čagatajsko-persidskij slovar' (New Chagatai-Persian dictionary) / In the collection: Mir-Ali-Shir. Leningrad, 1928, pp. 83-99.
15. Samoylovich A.N. Persidskiy tyurkolog XVIII veka Mirza Mekhdi-khan (Persian Turkologist of the 18th century Mirza Mehdi Khan) // News of the Society for the Survey and Study of Azerbaijan. № 5. Baku, 1927, p.3-12.
16. Samoylovich A.N. K istorii literaturnogo sredneaziatsko-turetskogo yazyka (On the history of the literary Central Asian Turkish language) / In the collection: Mir-Ali-Shir. - Leningrad, 1928, pp.1-13.
17. Senglax. A Persian Guide to the Turkish Language, by Muhammad Mahdi Xan. Facsimile text with an introduction and indicen by Sir Gerard Clauson. London, 1960.
18. Shcherbak A.M. Grammatika starouzbekskogo yazyka (Grammar of the Old Uzbek Language). – Moscow-Leningrad, Publishing House of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1962, pp.58-59.
19. Umarov Z.A. Grammatika starouzbekskogo yazyka “Mabani ul-lugat” Mirzy Mekhdikhana (Grammar of the Old Uzbek language “Mabani'l-Lughat” by Mirza Mehdi Khan): Abstract of the thesis. Tashkent, 1967, 27 p.

20. Vel'yaminov-Zernov V.V. Slovar' dzhagataysko-turetskiy (Dictionary of Jagatai-Turkish).
St. Petersburg: Printing House of the Imperial Academy of Sciences, 1868. — 440 pp.